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The use of 3D computer-assisted navigation and its influence on radiation exposure and operation time in the treatment of fragility fractures of the pelvis

DISSERTATION

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The use of 3D computer-assisted navigation and its influence on radiation exposure and operation time in the surgical treatment of fragility fractures of the pelvis

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Publikation

Abstract

Introduction

Percutaneous screw fixation is increasingly being used for stabilization of pelvic fragility fractures (FFP) in the elderly. Performing this procedure using 2D fluoroscopy is challenging due to the complex anatomy of the pelvis. 3D computer-assisted navigational imaging techniques have emerged to facilitate the procedure. This study compares traditional 2D fluoroscopy with 3D computer-assisted navigation regarding radiation exposure and operation time in patients with FFP.

Methods

This retrospective study included patients treated with percutaneous screws for FFP between 1st of January 2017, and 31th of May 2023. Patients were divided into two groups: those treated with conventional 2D fluoroscopy (2D-CF) and those with 3D computer-assisted navigation (3D-CAN). Data on demographics, ASA scores, fracture types and operative parameters were collected. The outcomes were intraoperative fluoroscopy time, operation time and complications. Statistical analyses were conducted, with statistical significance determined at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Eighteen patients were included in each group. There were no significant differences in baseline patient characteristics between the groups. Compared to 2D-CF (190.3 ± 86.9 seconds, $p=0.000$), 3D-CAN showed a significant reduction in fluoroscopy time (78.4 ± 33.7 seconds). The mean operative time was also significantly higher in 2D-CF (85.0 ± 28.1 minutes, $p=0.007$) versus 3D-CAN (62.1 ± 18.3 minutes). In 3D-CAN no screw-related complications were observed.

Conclusion

In surgical treatment of pelvis fragility fractures percutaneous screw fixation with 3D computer-assisted navigation systems significantly reduces patient radiation exposure and operative time in comparison to conventional intraoperative 2D imaging.

Key Words

Fragility fractures of the pelvis (FFP), hybrid operating rooms, non-hybrid operating rooms, radiation exposure and fluoroscopy.

Introduction

Fragility fractures of the pelvis (FFP) are an emerging concern among the elderly, accounting for approximately 7% of all osteoporotic fractures.(11, 19) It is suspected that the total incidence of osteoporotic fractures of the pelvis raises with 23% per year. These fractures are typically caused by low-energy trauma, such as a fall from standing height. In most cases, the ligaments remain intact, resulting in non-displaced or minimally displaced fractures.(32) However, despite the lack of significant displacement, the associated pain often leads to reduced mobility, which in turn is linked to higher rates of morbidity and mortality in this patient population(22, 28) (21, 26)

To facilitate early mobilization and alleviate pain, percutaneous screw fixation is increasingly being employed for FFP type II, III, and IV.(9, 15, 21, 29) In this already vulnerable patient population, minimizing the impact of surgery by improving procedural efficiency and accuracy is crucial. Traditionally, 2D fluoroscopy has been the standard imaging technique for performing percutaneous screw fixation.(3, 30, 34) However, this approach is challenged by the three-dimensional complexity of the pelvis, the inherent limitations of osseous corridors, and the variability caused by sacral dysmorphism.(4) Additionally, frequent intraoperative adjustments to the 2D fluoroscope are required to achieve the correct views, which not only prolongs the surgical procedure but also significantly increases radiation exposure for both the patient and the surgical team.

To overcome these challenges, more recently, advanced surgical imaging techniques have been increasingly incorporated into the treatment of FFP fractures, including computed tomography (CT) navigation, 2D or 3D navigation, and robotic navigation.(1, 16, 23, 24, 26, 37, 38) These innovative techniques offer potential advantages, such as enhancing imaging efficiency and, consequently, reducing both radiation exposure and operation time. A recent meta-analysis focused on accuracy, showed a tendency towards a higher accuracy for more advanced navigation techniques such as O-arm, 3D CT and robotic navigation.(8) Higher accuracy indirectly leads to less complications.(1) Furthermore, the use of a hybrid operating room could especially reduce the radiation dose to the surgical staff, enhancing occupational safety.(31) Reduction of operation time is critical in this vulnerable patient group.

However, data on radiation exposure and operation times remain underreported. (2, 20)

Therefore, this study aims to compare traditional 2D fluoroscopy with 3D computer-assisted navigation regarding radiation exposure and operation time in patients with fragility fractures undergoing treatment with percutaneous SI screws.

Methods

Study setting and participants

All consecutive patients with fragility fractures of the pelvis treated with percutaneous screw fixation at a level 1 trauma center in Switzerland, between 01.01.2017 and 31.05.2023 were included. Excluded were patients with high-energy traumas, patients who had surgical treatment for fractures apart the pelvis during the same surgery, open fractures, revision surgeries or absent informed consent.

Study design

The study was designed as a pre-post observational study in a single center. Patients were categorized in two groups according to the intraoperative imaging technique used. The first group were patients who were operated on with the help of conventional fluoroscopy (2D-CF) prior to the introduction of the 3D computer navigated system. The second group were patients who were operated on with the help of 3D computer-assisted navigation (3D-CAN). After the introduction of 3D-CAN, 2D-CF was not performed anymore. Therefore, the two techniques did not co-exist. To eliminate differences in surgical technique or experience, only surgeries from one experienced senior pelvic surgeon were selected. To minimize the impact of a potential learning curve, patients were included in consecutive chronological order from the most recent to the older cases. For patients in the 2D-CF group, this was done until the implementation of a new hospital record system that facilitated data collection. In other words, for both techniques, these were the last cases of the 2D-CF and 3D-CAN groups.

Baseline characteristics

Baseline characteristics including demographic data (sex, age, ASA score, FFP classification), clinical history and surgery specific parameters (number of S1 and/or S2 screws, os pubis screws, volume of cement used in ml (mean)) were collected.(27, 36)

All data were extracted from the Merlin Diagnostics Program (version 7) and EPIC Hyperspace Production Program (version 100.2410.4.0). These software applications are employed routinely for comprehensive data management and analysis.

Imaging technique

In the 2D-CF group conventional fluoroscopy is used. In contrast to 3D-CAN, the fluoroscopy has to be positioned manually and adjusted manually after switching between inlet, outlet or lateral views. Due to the lack of navigation and the possibility of doing an intraoperative CT scan, a postoperative CT scan is necessary to check the screw placement.

In the 3D-CAN group the surgical room is equipped with a mobile CT-arm, which can be moved freely around the patient. Conventional fluoroscopic images as well as CT

images are possible to conduct during surgery. The first advantage of this system is the possibility to plan the screws prior to surgery and use this planning for active guidance during surgery. The second advantage is the possibility of defining a personalized lateral, inlet and outlet view for every patient.(15) Those predefined views are saved by the software system to allow swift intraoperative transition between these views, allowing for consistency and efficacy during the procedure. Correct placement of the screws can easily be verified with an intraoperative CT scan if necessary. Radiation protection shields (RPS) are strategically positioned to reduce radiation exposure for the surgical team.

Surgical Technique

Apart from the imaging technique, the surgical technique for SI screws does not differ between the two groups. The surgery is carried out with the patient positioned in a supine position. A percutaneous K-wire is placed dorsally from lateral. Correct K-wire placement is either based on anatomical landmarks (2D-CF) and/or navigation (3D-CAN). After correct placement, a screw is inserted over the K-wire. After removal of the K-wire, augmentation can be performed with polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) cement. If a contralateral or additional ipsilateral screw is desired, augmentation is performed after all posterior screws are placed. Possible iliosacral screw placement options are in the sacral body of S1, S2, bilateral or transsacral. Fixation of the anterior fractures is optional and is performed in a retrograde manner. Bilateral anterior fixation can be performed over a single incision. A detailed description of this technique in a hybrid room with 3D computer-assisted navigation is described by Link et al.(6, 15)

Outcomes

The outcomes of interest were intraoperative fluoroscopy time (measured in seconds, mean), total operation time (measured in minutes, mean), and all reported complications. Data on fluoroscopy or surgery time per screw was unavailable, as only total surgery duration was provided. Consequently, we estimated the time per screw by dividing the total operation and fluoroscopy time by the number of screws placed.

Complications were categorized into three groups: general complications (e.g., infection, death), surgery-related complications (e.g., intraoperative or postoperative bleeding, surgical site infections), and screw-related complications (e.g., screw loosening, dislocation, or cement leakage).

Statistical methods

SPSS (IBM SPSS Statistics, version 25) was utilized for statistical analysis, comparing various variables between the two groups. The results for all assessed parameters were reported using means, median, range, or percentage, as deemed suitable.

For the baseline parameters, the Chi-Square test was utilized for binary queries, whereas the Mann-Whitney U-test was more suitable for non-normally distributed continuous data to assess the significance between outcomes. Statistical significance was conferred upon probabilities with a p-value below 0.05.

Results

Number (n)	2D-CF (18)	3D-CAN(18)	P
Age, years (mean ± SD)	81.8 ± 12.3	83.6 ± 9.4	0.621
Female, n (%)	16 (88.9)	17 (94.4)	0.560
ASA – classification (mean ± SD)	2.78 ± 0.73	2.78 ± 0.64	1.00
FFP classification			0.478
FFP II, n (%)	12 (66.7)	13 (72.2)	
FFP III, n (%)	3 (16.7)	4 (22.2)	
FFP IV, n (%)	3 (16.7)	1 (5.6)	

Table 1. patient characteristics

Baseline characteristics

18 patients were included in 2D-CF and 18 patients in 3D-CAN. There were no significant differences in patient characteristics between the two groups. (Table 1) The majority of patients in both groups were female and over 80 years old. Approximately 70% of fractures were type II in both groups

Surgical data

Number (n)	2D-CF (18)	3D-CAN (18)	P
Amount of cement in ml (mean ± SD)	2.5 ± 1.6	2.5 ± 0.7	0.990
Amount of screws (n)			
S1 screw	27	31	0.044
Unilateral	9	3	
Bilateral	9	14	
Additional S2 screw	0	5	
Os pubis screw	18	19	0.933
Unilateral	12	13	
Bilateral	3	3	
Total	45	56	

Table 2. amount of cement and amount of screws 2D-CF versus 3D-CAN

Intraoperative details are presented in table 2. The total amount of screws placed in 2D-CF was 45 screws (27 screws posterior and 18 screws anterior). In 3D-CAN, this was higher with 55 screws in total (36 posterior and 19 anterior). In 2D-CF no S2 screws were placed, whereas in 3D-CAN 5 additional S2 screws were placed. The total amount of cement used per surgery was 2.5 ± 1.6 ml in 2D-CF and 2.5 ± 0.7 ml in 3D-CAN (p=0.990).

Radiation

Number (n)	2D-CF (n)	3D-CAN (n)	P
Operation time in minutes (mean ± SD)	85.0 ± 28.1 (18)	62.1 ± 18.3 (17)	0.007
2 screws	70.6 ± 19.4 (10)	39.0 ± 4.2 (2)	
3 screws	89.7 ± 9.2 (6)	56.6 ± 13.1 (9)	
4 screws	143.0 ± 26.9 (2)	78.0 ± 14.8 (6)	
Fluoroscopy time in seconds (mean ± SD)	190.3 ± 86.9 (18)	78.4 ± 33.7 (16)	0.000
2 screws	134.7 ± 64.6 (10)	56.5 ± 5.0 (2)	
3 screws	239.7 ± 46.7 (6)	72.4 ± 28.8 (8)	
4 screws	320.5 ± 17.7 (2)	93.7 ± 41.2 (6)	

Table 3. operation and fluoroscopy time

In 2D-CF, the mean operative time was 85 ± 28.1 minutes, which was significantly longer than the 62.1 ± 18.3 minutes recorded in 3D-CAN (p=0.007) (table 3). Fluoroscopy time in seconds was used to compare the radiation exposure in both groups (table 3). This was significantly lower in the 3D-CAN group (78.4 ± 33.7 seconds) compared to the 2D-CF (190.3 ± 86.9 seconds).

Complications

Complication	2D-CF (18)	3D-CAN (18)
General complications		
Bleeding postoperative (n)	0	1
Surgical site infection (n)	0	0
Postoperative infection (n)	0	1
Screw related complications		
Screw penetration (n)	1	0
Screw dislocation (n)	2	0
Cement leakage (n)	1	0

Table 4. complications

There were in total four surgery related complications and two general complications (Table 4). Within 2D-CF, no cases of postoperative bleeding were documented, while with 3D-CAN one postoperative bleeding was reported. This was treated conservatively with local pressure. No surgical site infections occurred in either groups. However, one postoperative pneumonia occurred in 3D-CAN which was treated effectively with antibiotics.

Regarding screw-related complications, one patient in 2D-CF group experienced screw penetration. This patient remained asymptomatic. No instances were recorded within the 3D-CAN group. In 2D-CF, two cases of screw dislocation were observed. One of these patients was asymptomatic and in the other the screw was removed due to pain. In 3D-CAN no occurrences of screw dislocation were observed.

Regarding cement-related complications, one case of cement leakage was noted in 2D-CF, while 3D-CAN displayed none. However, this single patient remained asymptomatic, experiencing no pain, sensory or motor deficits, and showing no evidence of fracture non-union.

Discussion

This retrospective cohort study compared 2D-CF to 3D-CAN regarding fluoroscopy time and operative time in patients treated with percutaneous SI-screws for fragility fractures of the pelvis. A clear reduction of 59% in fluoroscopy time (190.3 seconds versus 78.4 seconds) and 27% in operative time (85 minutes versus 62.1 minutes) was shown in favor of 3D-CAN. Although rare in both groups, screw related complications were slightly more prevalent among the 2D-CF group. This, however, did not reach statistical significance.

Comparison to previous literature

3D-CAN is increasingly used in orthopedic and trauma surgery, particularly in spine or pelvic procedures. (25) Numerous studies have examined its effects on radiation exposure and operative time, with findings largely consistent with ours. (23, 24, 38) Three studies reported reductions in fluoroscopy time when using 3D-CAN, ranging from 42.7% to 66.9%. Such consistency across multiple studies and across multiple fields emphasized the value of integrating 3D-CAN in the treatment of FFP. However, not all studies showed reduced operation times with 3D-CAN. In some cases, particularly during early technology adoption, operative times increased by 4.3% to 49.1% compared to 2D-CF, possibly due to a learning curve effect. (1, 12, 13, 37) Conversely, other navigation systems, such as robotic or O-arm navigation, have shown reductions in operative time, from 8.9% to 53.8%, which may be attributed to more streamlined workflows and experienced teams. (14, 16, 17) In vascular surgery using similar 3D-CAN with a tailored workflow lead to a reduced radiation exposure. (7)

Other studies comparing different radiological systems with 3D-CAN also highlight that staff positioning and optimal use of freestanding radiation protection shields can further reduce radiation doses by over 22%. (10) This emphasizes the importance of standardized protocols. (33)

Interpretation of results

Based on the results, 3D-CAN significantly reduces both operation time and radiation exposure compared to 2D-CF. Certain aspects, however, should be acknowledged.

The observed difference in radiation exposure is expected to be even greater than reported for two reasons. First, patients undergo a postoperative CT scan following 2D-CF, which was not included in the initial calculations. Second, the total radiation exposure in the 3D CT group applies only to the patient, as the surgical team exits the room during the intraoperative CT scan and is therefore not exposed to the full radiation dose that the patient receives. Nevertheless, fluoroscopy time is inferior to radiation dose measured in gray and results should be interpreted with caution.

Regarding operative time, this study measured total operative time, but exact time per screw was not directly recorded. We estimated this by dividing total time by the number of screws placed, which provides a reasonable approximation. The 27% reduction in operative time suggests a genuine benefit of 3D-CAN, likely due to the ability to individually store and restore C-arm positions and radiologic presets as needed what reduces the need for screw and C-arm adjustments.

This study shows that complications are rare in both 2D-CF and 3D-CAN. Screw related complications rarely have clinical implications. In 2D-CF four cases of screw-

related complications occurred, whereas in 3D-CAN, there were no cases of screw penetration or dislocation. This may suggest a potential advantage in terms of a higher accuracy and therefore less screw-related complications in 3D-CAN. (30, 31) (18, 35)

This study could not detect a difference in systemic complications. Existing literature indicates a clear relationship between prolonged operative time and the development of systemic complications, such as pneumonia, infection or post-operative myocardial infarction.⁽⁵⁾ As operative time was shorter, it may be expected that this will also have an influence on the risk of these complications. The fact that we did not detect this difference might have been caused by a small sample size.

Limitations

Some limitations must be acknowledged. First, the small sample size and the method used to estimate time per screw placement (dividing total operative time by the number of screws) can only provide an approximation of the operative time per screw but not the exact time. Prospective studies on time per screw would be valuable addressing this aspect more comprehensively. Second, incomplete documentation of complications also makes it challenging to accurately compare complication rates between the 3D-CAN and 2D-CF groups. Therefore, caution is advised when interpreting these results. Third, we chose to analyze only the cases of a single expert surgeon to minimize the impact of a learning curve and other confounding variables. While this approach limits the generalizability of the study, it makes the findings more focused, consistent, and reliable.

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential benefits of using 3D-CAN for surgical treatment of FFP, showing that it significantly reduces both radiation exposure and operation time compared to 2D-CF, while maintaining a low complication rate.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Björn-Christian Link is a Siemens Healthcare consultant.

All the other authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained 2024-00107 (EKNZ)

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